

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PHRASEOLOGICAL FUND OF ENGLISH AND FRENCH LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to a comparative analysis of the phraseological resource of the English and French languages. The main goal of the work is to do a comparative analysis of the phraseological units of the English and French languages with the same type of components and to consider the phraseological units in separate thematic groups, to identify the differences between the linguistic landscapes of the English and French languages.

Linguistic and cultural factors in the language, as well as the oral communication of representatives of different cultures, further expand the possibilities of researching the phraseology of foreign languages. In our research, the comparative analysis of phraseological units of English and French languages with the same type of components and consideration of phraseological units in separate thematic groups allows to identify the differences between the linguistic landscapes of English and French languages.

Studying the phraseological landscape of the English and French world helps to understand the character traits of people, to distinguish between the characteristics that are unique to the English and the French, and at the same time to identify many similar norms of etiquette. Analyzing the concept of "phraseological image" is of particular importance in the formation of phraseological meaning.

The formation of phraseological units usually occurs on a figurative-metaphorical basis, so it can be argued that phraseological units actively participate in the formation of the linguistic landscape of world and national cultures. The analysis of figurative-motivational bases helps to reveal the national culture in phraseological units, because, as mentioned above, phraseological units reflect the mentality of people.

In a number of works of L.I. Rozeyzon, E.A. Malinovsky, A.D. Khayutin, only the term phraseology is mentioned, the term idioms is not mentioned at all. The examples presented in these studies show that phraseology is understood as both idioms and expressions of a terminological character, proverbial proverbs, artistic clichés, and memoirs.¹

¹ Roseison L.I., E.A. Malinovsky, A.D. Khayutin "Essays on the history of the formation of phraseology as a linguistic discipline", Samarkand 1975. – C. 5.

According to researchers, the distinguishing feature of an idiom is that the meaning of an idiom is not equal to the meaning of its constituent parts. For example, the meaning of the word "slack" is not derived from the words "later" and "sleeves" separately. This makes an idiom "a feature of only one language". (ironing is an exception). Therefore, the consideration of phraseology in the English language should begin with idiomatic expressions, the meaning of which, in our opinion, does not come from its components. For example, "to kill two birds with one stone - (Uzbek equivalent) bir o'q bilan ikki quyovni urmoq" does not correspond to the original meaning of the words: to kill, bird, stone is part of this phrase. The meaning of this combination cannot be translated literally into French. But both in French and in English, this expression has its own way of conveying meaning, which is to achieve a goal through small meanings.

Thus, idioms are clearly distinguished from the rest of the semantically global word equivalents, which are formed separately, and are a fully researched part of the phraseology of the English and French languages. There are also many dictionaries and thesauruses of English idioms, which not only contain English phrases, but also provide the most important information for understanding how the corresponding phrase entered the language, the basis of its appearance is connected with which field of human activity. The function of fixed phrases in English, their features of re-formation and assessment from the point of view of linguistic norms depend on socio-historical factors. Literary English people rarely use idioms in their speech, considering them to be impure stereotypical clichés. At the same time, the use of phraseology, on the contrary, is evaluated by Englishmen as one of the fluent and lively manifestations of speech.

As an example, we give a passage from the novel "The Razor's Edge" by S. Maugham. It is condemned that the hero of the work is addicted to expressions that have lost their originality. Gray's dialogue is limited to clichés - *Gray's conversation was composed of clichés. However shopworn, he uttered them with an obvious conviction that he was the first person to think of them. He never went to bed, but hit the hay, where he slept the sleep of the just; if it rained, it rained to beat the band and to the very end Paris to him was Gay Paree* (S. Maugham, The Razor's Edge).

Each generation of the English and French people observed the world, people's social and family relationships, and these observations were reflected in the poetry of folk folklore. It can be emphasized that in any other genre of folklore, the life of the people is not reflected as wide and multifaceted as in the paremias, they can be called an encyclopedia of the life of the people, because they echo many historical events and facts. Paremias reflect family and social life, worldview of people with all their strengths and weaknesses, wisdom and historical events, reasons and opinions.

Most of the proverbs acquire a figurative meaning based on the generalization of isolated facts, which in many cases is the motivational basis of the direct meaning and allows for deep interpretation of the proverbs. In some cases, phraseological units reflect the personal experiences of the author and also serve as an object of knowledge.

At the same time, it should be mentioned that people communicate with each other due to the existence of a common language system. Proverbs are a particular part of this system. The universal and ethnocultural character of phraseological units is revealed only in the

content when the semantic structure of the researched units and the semantics of the names of the religious concepts expressed in them are compared with the ethnic concepts and the descriptive features are analyzed.

The history of English and French phraseology depends on the perception of the world by a person of French and English origin. The French are known for their love of luxury, refined taste and unique French charm. This is also reflected in the phraseology of the French language:

arbiter des élégances(or dugoût) (french.) – - trendsetter.

faire ses délices de qch. (french.) – find the greatest pleasure in anything.

bouche delicate (French) - gourmet.

avoir le palais fin (or délicat) (French) - have a delicate taste.

le vert galant – masher.

soutenu (or élevé, noble) style – high style.

The English are distinguished by their strictness, their adherence to Puritan morals, and their boring talk about the weather. There are many phraseological units in English that confirm these points.

king's weather – wonderful weather

after rain comes fair weather (last) - after bad weather - the sun, after grief - joy.

the rain comes down in torrents – it rains pitchforks

rain or shine – come hell or high water²

Phraseological units derived from Latin and Greek languages are mainly bookish in nature. In this study, examples from the French language were given:

1) *Affair of honor (eng.)* – "Matter of honor", duel;– *Affaire d'honneur (french.)*.

2) *Affair of heart (eng.)* – matters of the heart, romance; –*Affair de coeur (french.)*.

3) *There's a woman in it (English)* - "look for a woman";– *Chercher la femme (french.)*.

The above examples preserve the way in which English and French phraseology is enriched and interlaced. This story cannot be described without studying the historical legacy of the English and French peoples. It should be used that includes English and French.

In our study, we chose such differences to show the difference between these peoples, their behavior in society, customs and traditions. It can be seen that all this is not without reflection in the fund and phraseology of the English and French languages.

The following examples show French proverbs that have changed in English:

1) *C'est dans la nécessité que l'on connaît ses vrais amis (French.)/ A friend in need is a friend (English)*

2) *Chien qui aboie, ne mord pas (French.)/ Barking dogs seldom bite (English).*

3) *Il n'est pas aussi diable qu'il est noir (French.)/ The devil is not so black as he is painted (English).*

4) *Il n'y a pas de fumée sans feu (French.)/ There is no smoke without fire (English).*

Changes in language do not always translate into changes in behavior. Therefore, when learning a certain language, it is necessary to teach the culture of the country being studied

² Гак. В.Г. Новый большой французско-русский фразеологический словарь. –М.: Русский язык. 2005. – 1624 с.

along with the language, so that the foreign culture does not influence the behavior. When learning a foreign language, communication takes place between two different cultures. Therefore, each language allows to study the cultural values of a particular nation.

The fact that the cultures of the English and French peoples are very similar to each other proves the commonality between these peoples. This is particularly evident in phraseology, which is a part of national traditions reflected in people's daily life. English and French phraseological units call for respect for parents, proper upbringing of children, appreciation of friendship, high concepts of honor and moral purity, as well as consideration for adults. Also, phraseological units condemn and satirize people's vices and weaknesses.

The English phraseological fund has increased significantly due to expressions borrowed from the French language. Taking into account that the structure of the phraseological landscape of the world is formed by phraseological units representing objective world realities, we put forward the idea of the thematic-ideographic concept as the main principle of classifying phraseological units.

The formation of phraseological units usually takes place on the basis of figurative-metaphor, so it can be said that phraseological units actively enrich and attract the linguistic landscape of the world of English and French peoples. Analysis of figurative and motivational bases of phraseological units helps to reveal national and cultural components in them. This, in turn, reflects the people's worldview.

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